

THE ROLE OF WARM-UP ACTIVITIES DURING LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Annotation

There are abundant ways and techniques to make language classes more easily comprehensible and intriguing. This article is devoted to discuss one of these effective methods which is organizing warm-up activities and their benefits to learners.

Key words: warm-up activities, language classes, learners' motivation, students' attention

Language learning is really constant and grueling process which makes many students loath to study. In order not to make learners reluctant to learn a language, teachers need to find out exiting and engrossing ways of teaching a language. If students are not interested in a class, they are likely to give up or make a progress quite slowly. To this end, warm-up activities can be an effective means of motivating learners and grabbing their attention.

What is a warm-up?

A warm-up is an activity that is conducted at beginning of a class to prepare students for upcoming activities by stimulating their minds or brains. According to Rushidi, a warm-up stage is a preparatory stage which helps the students feel relaxed and also sets a positive mood for learning (Rushidi, 2013). In other words, it is an introductory part of a lesson in which students both physically and mentally get ready for main parts of a class by means of short and fun games.

In what ways warm-up activities can be useful?

1. Motivation

As it is mentioned above, language learning is not an easy process, and therefore, students feel bored during a lesson which is held in a monotonous way. Teachers can foster learners' motivation by applying various language related activities and guarantee potential success of students in language learning. Garcia and Martin stated that by spending five or ten minutes for warm up activities, learners can be motivated from the beginning of a class (García, 2004). Maintaining a high level of motivation during a period of language learning is one of the best ways to make the whole process more successful (Patricia, 2010).

2. Attention

One of the main problems that language learners and teachers often come across is short-attention span or losing attention completely during language classroom. The primary reason of it can be a feeling of boredom, and one clue is using warming up activities. They will cause people to stop whatever they are doing or thinking and refocus their attention (Velandia, 2008). Should a teacher grab students' attention from scratch, it may set the tone for the rest of a class and learners can be able to understand topics and master a language effortlessly and willingly.

3. Creativity

Another benefit of warm-up activities is increased creativity. Students especially young learners can discover for themselves new interesting ways of acquiring a language and use them in the future as a supplementary learning tool. Additionally, warm-up activities are not only handy in language classroom, but also they can be applied in any field. Therefore, students have a tendency to use such activities that they learn in language classes in different ways for a long time.

Aforementioned benefits of warm-up activities were claimed by plenty of researchers. One of the thorough studies carried by Rosalba Velandia in which seven graders, who were uninterested in English classes, examined to claim the effectiveness of warm-up activities. Based on the results collected mainly from the field notes, these kinds of activities really appear to promote students' involvement in the English class (Velandia, 2008). Another study devoted to investigate that topic was by Mohammadreza Khodareza in 2011. 60 sophomore EFL students were checked by doing pretests and protests and their scores were analyzed under scrutiny. The findings revealed that participants in the experimental group, who had received the treatments on warm up tasks, significantly enhanced better performance in a writing test (Khodareza, 2011). The other research stated that using an easy activity at the beginning help the students solve the activity easily and motivate them to participate in further activities (Akther, 2014).

Considering all benefits and research findings that were given above, it can be concluded that using warm-up activities during language classroom is really constructive way to start a class and set an enthusiastic tone for the whole lesson. Warm-up activities have an immense effect on learners no matter what their levels and ages if they are used in a right way. Although some teachers tend to underestimate their values, it is highly recommended to use such activities on a regular basis as a supplementary teaching and learning tool.

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